

ULTRA-LOW-LATENCY FPGA-ACCELERATED NEURAL NETWORK INFERENCE AT 40 MHZ AT CMS

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ABSTRACT

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In the realm of data processing and physics analysis at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC), deep learning based algorithms have proven to be more advantageous than traditional physics based algorithms in certain cases [2]. This study explores cutting-edge methodologies for the low latency neural network inference on Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) devices. Specifically, the study focuses on muon primitive recalibration and fake/real muon pair classification at the rate of 40 MHz within the CMS L1 trigger system. The primary objective of this work is to develop an low-latency neural network model, strategically combining various techniques such as quantization aware training, knowledge distillation, transfer learning, and pruning schedules to reduce the computational footprint when compared to the preexisting baseline while simultaneously improving on reconstruction performance. Using the said strategy, the models were compressed over four times while still achieving significantly lower error rates than given baselines.

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1 Introduction

The Large Hadron Collider (LHC) is one of the most sophisticated experiments ever designed. Its main purpose is to probe the internal structures of matter and study the underlying physics and interactions of the particles that make up our universe. The LHC simulates conditions that existed shortly after the Big Bang by colliding particles travelling close to the speed of light. Particles collide at LHC at a rate of 40 MHz, generating huge amounts of data every second. Two proton beams travel opposite directions along the LHC (27 km ring of superconducting agents) and collide at four specific points (with 13 TeV of energy in the centre of the mass frame) where sophisticated detectors (ATLAS at point 1, ALICE at point 2, CMS at point 5, and LHCb at point 8) are located. In this work, the Compact Muon Solenoid (CMS) experiment is considered (we discuss in section 1.1).

CMS generates data at a theoretical throughput of $\mathcal{O}(40)$ TB/s. It is not possible to store or read out the full event record at such a rate; therefore, a triggering system is required to select interesting events from these huge amounts of data. At CMS we have a two level triggering system, a Level-1 (L1) trigger running on FPGA hardware, performing a coarse and partial reconstruction of the events, and a High-Level-Trigger (HLT), running on CPU and GPU farms, that runs the full event reconstruction and selects down to an output rate orders of magnitude smaller than the initial input rate to the trigger system. The triggering system at CMS is described in detail in section 1.2.

Traditionally, physics-based algorithms were used in the triggering system. However, given the massive success of machine learning (ML) and deep learning, it is important to investigate if an ML-based algorithm can be a aid in the triggering system. Since most of the triggering system is on FGPA-based computational hardware, computational footprint and timing constraints should also be kept in mind. This work shows how ML-based triggering algorithms can be designed that are both computationally lighter and have superior performances compared to traditional physics-based algorithms on tasks such as online recalibration of physics objects and classification of di-muon pairs. Moreover, its is also shown how ML-based algorithms can be used in search of beyond standard model particles (dark photons) in an extension to this study.

1.1 The Compact Muon Solenoid experiment

The Compact Muon Solenoid (CMS) is a general-purpose detector used for Standard Model (SM) physics and Beyond Standard Model (BSM) searches. The CMS detector is composed of cylindrical layers of subdetectors for various purposes. The innermost layer is the silicon tracking system, which consists of the pixel and strip detectors used to detect and reconstruct the tracks and interaction vertices of charged particles. Outside of the tracking system are the electromagnetic calorimeter (ECAL) and the hadronic calorimeter (HCAL), used to measure the energy of electromagnetically interacting particles and hadrons, respectively. The subsystems are then surrounded by a large solenoid magnet providing a peak magnetic field of 3.8 T at the centre of the detector. This aims to measure transverse momentum (described in section 2.1) for charged particles by bending their trajectories. The final layer is the muon detector. A comprehensive description of the CMS detector can be found in Figure 1

1.2 The triggering system at CMS

The bunch crossing rate at CMS is 40 MHz. Considering the average size of $\mathcal{O}(1)$ MB for a recorded collision, the CMS detector produces over 40 TB/s of data when working in peak

Figure 1: Compact Muon Solenoid [3]

conditions. The permanent storage can only handle events at a rate of $\mathcal{O}(10^3)$ Hz, thus an event rate reduction of a factor $\mathcal{O}(10^5)$ is required. A two-step triggering system schematised in figure 2, is used to achieve this task.

Level-1 Trigger — The first triggering stage works at a fixed latency of $3.2 \mu\text{s}$, reducing the event rate from 40 MHz to a maximum of 110 KHz. Given the rate of data and timing constraints, the codes must be run on devices working with a fixed latency; hence, the L1 trigger is implemented on FPGA hardware. The L1 trigger is divided into muon and calorimeter trigger subsystems, running a coarse reconstruction of the muon, hadronic and leptonic primitives, respectively. The primitives are then sent to a global trigger, where hundreds of algorithms check whether the event is potentially interesting for physics studies; otherwise, they are discarded. This feature implies that the L1 trigger only covers part of the phase space of the possible physics scenarios. Thus, the study of exotic physics signatures, like soft displaced leptons and slow heavy stable charged particles spanning multiple BXs, might be affected by this bias.

High-Level-Trigger — The second stage of the triggering system (HLT) reduces the event rate further from 100 KHz to around 1 KHz, at which the data can be permanently stored. The HLT runs on a farm of CPUs and GPUs. The HLT receives the full information from the entire detector, allowing a full physics reconstruction.

Figure 2: CMS Trigger system and L1 Scouting system.[10]

2 Definitions and preliminaries

The following section introduces various specific definitions and preliminary concepts that are used frequently in the study before moving to the methods and relevant results presentation..

2.1 L1 muon primitives kinematic parameters

The main kinematic parameters of the L1 muon primitives coming from μ GMT, used for subsequent analysis, are listed and described below:

- **the transverse momentum p_T** : it is the component of the momentum of a particle in the xy plane. Which can be denoted by $p_T = \sqrt{p_X^2 + p_Y^2}$
- **the azimuth angle ϕ** : this is defined as the angle between the transverse momentum in the xy plane and the x -axis;
- **the pseudorapidity η** : given the polar angle θ between the y -axis and and the momentum, η is defined as $\eta = -\log[\tan(\frac{\theta}{2})]$;

The reference system used to describe the CMS experiment is illustrated in Figure 3

Figure 3: Reference system for momentum [5]

2.2 Neural Networks

Neural networks are a paradigm of machine learning technique that uses neuron-like structures, inspired by biological neurons, to teach computers to process data, understand patterns, and decipher hidden meaning from raw data.

Structure — Figure 4 shows a neural network with three hidden layers and n of neurons per layer. Each node in a layer is fed with the information from all the previous layers' nodes. The nodes of the neural networks represent a pair of weights and a bias (essentially elements of linear transformation) that can be learned through loss minimisation by the gradient descent algorithm. Each node can be considered a transformation $w^T x + b$, on x , where w^T is the weight matrix, and b is the corresponding bias. The weights for the first layer can be written as:

$$X^l = \text{Act}(\omega_l^T X^{l-1} + b_l) \quad , \quad (1)$$

$$X^l = \{X_1^l, X_2^l, \dots, X_n^l\} \quad , \quad (2)$$

where X^{l-1} is the feature vector of $(l-1)$ -th layer, ω_l and b_l are the learnable weights and biases for layer l and Act is the activation function. The non-linear ReLU activation [1], defined as:

$$\text{ReLU}(x) = \max(0, x) \quad , \quad (3)$$

has been mainly employed for this work. The outputs of a neural network can be similarly calculated using the feature vectors from the final layer.

Figure 4: Neural Networks [13]

Loss Function — A mathematical way to quantify the difference between the true and the predicted values from the neural network is needed to tune its trainable parameters. This task is accomplished through the definition of a loss function. The gradient taken along the loss function is then used in the gradient descent optimization algorithm to perform the tuning:

$$W \leftarrow W - \alpha \nabla \lambda(Y, \hat{Y}) \quad , \tag{4}$$

where λ is the loss function, \hat{Y} is the neural networks prediction and α is a hyper-parameter called learning rate.

2.3 Quantization Aware Training (QAT)

Only the fixed point numerical precision is supported by the FPGA device selected for this work. On the other hand, a general neural network defined in the previous section is often a function with real value output and involving 32-bit floating point (FP-32) precision operations. This characteristic makes them inherently difficult to deploy on FPGA boards. This can be fixed by training the model in quantization-aware mode, i.e. quantization-aware training (QAT) [9]. QAT makes the model more suitable for FPGA boards and leads to a lighter model since the calculations are not done in full precision. QAT achieves this by simulating a quantised model during the forward pass. This causes quantisation losses to accumulate. During the backward pass, the model learns parameters that are robust to quantisation.

2.4 Knowledge Distillation

Knowledge distillation [7] is a method in deep learning that is often used to compress over-parameterised models to lightweight and under-parameterised ones. In this work, offline knowledge distillation is used to compress the models. Offline knowledge distillation relies on the principle of using a large over-parameterised pre-trained teacher model to train a much lighter student model. The teacher is pre-trained on the entire dataset. The number of parameters in the teacher is increased until the performance gain plateaus. Once the teacher is trained, the weights are frozen. A much smaller student model is initialised and the knowledge from the teacher is distilled to the student. Consider the objective to learn the mapping $X \rightarrow Y$. Now we define

$$f_t \equiv \text{Teacher Network} \quad , \tag{5}$$

$$f_s \equiv \text{Student Network} \quad , \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbb{L}_t \equiv \text{Task Agnostic Loss Function} \quad , \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbb{L}_d \equiv \text{Distillation Loss Function} \quad , \quad (8)$$

$$\text{loss}(X, Y) = \alpha \cdot \mathbb{L}_t(f_s(X), Y) + (1 - \alpha) \mathbb{L}_d(f_s(X), f_t(X)) \quad . \quad (9)$$

In the above equations α is the distillation parameter that is assigned a value between 0 and 1.

2.5 Metrics

Various metrics are used to compare the performance (computational cost) and resolution (prediction accuracy) of different models. The following metrics are defined that will be used extensively later on. For regression tasks, the metric employed is the Full-Width-Half-Maximum (FWHM), which reads:

$$\text{FWHM}_Y = \text{FWHM}(\hat{y}_i - y_i) \quad . \quad (10)$$

For classification tasks, the Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic curve (AUC-ROC) score is chosen as metric. To measure the computational cost of our model on the FPGAs we will use the following metrics:

- **Digital Signal Processors (DSP):** DSP chips are used for processing the relevant signals coming to the FPGA board, particularly additions and multiplications.
- **Flip Flops (FF):** these units help synchronise logic and save logical states between clock cycles within an FPGA circuit;
- **Look-up-Tables (LUT):** the units help in implementing arbitrary boolean logics inside the FPGA;
- **Block RAM (BRAM):** a type of random access memory implemented inside the FPGA for data storage.

The number of these resources available is greatly limited. Hence models with the least amount of resource consumption are given a higher priority.

3 μ GMT muons recalibration

Recalibrating of μ , ϕ and p_T using the L1 parameters μ , ϕ , p_T , muon charge and reconstruction quality is one of the primary focus of this study. Offline reconstruction data is used as ground truth for training the networks. Knowledge distillation along with QAT is used to achieve a high level of reconstruction resolution by only using a fraction of resources on the FPGA boards.

Teacher Model — A four-hidden layers neural network with 256 neurons in each layer is chosen as the teacher model. ReLU [1] non-linearity is used along with batch-normalization [8] after every subsequent layer. The output layer consists of three parameters that predict the recalibrated μ , ϕ and p_T . QKeras [12] is used to train the models with QAT precision fixed at [18,6]. Fixed precision notation is used throughout the work, where the leftmost digit signifies the total number of bits used to store the number while the rightmost digit represents the number of bits used to store the fractional part. The model is trained for 100 epochs using LogCosh loss, and the learning rate is reduced after the model performance plateaus. The Adam [11] optimiser is used with an initial learning rate of 10^{-4} .

Student Model — A four-hidden layers neural network with 8 neurons in each layer is chosen as the student model. ReLU non-linearity is used along with batch-normalization after every subsequent layer. The output layer consists of three parameters that predict the recalibrated μ , ϕ and p_T . QKeras is used to train the model with QAT precision fixed at [18,6]. The model is trained for 500 epochs with LogCosh as the task agnostic loss and mean square error (MSE) as the distillation loss, the distillation parameter α is fixed to 0.1 and the learning rate is reduced after the model performance plateaus. Adam optimiser is used with an initial learning rate of 10^{-2} .

Baseline Model — To compare the effectiveness of the proposed method, the above models are compared with the existing baselines in terms of both reconstruction resolution and computational requirements. The reported model from [4] is used as the baseline for this study. The model is a four-hidden-layer neural network with 16 neurons in each layer trained with similar loss and schedule as the teacher model.

FWHM	Teacher	Student	Baseline
ϕ	0.120	0.1240	0.140
η	0.061	0.063	0.0662
p_T	0.413	0.417	0.433

Table 1: Below Table shows the performance of the three models across the three parameters ϕ, η and p_T . Although the student is much smaller than the teacher, it performs almost as well as it. It outperforms the baseline by a large margin even though it is four times lighter.

3.1 Analysis of the student model performance

Although the student model outperforms the baseline across all the metrics still a deeper understanding of the performance is required before moving forward. This section looks into the μ GMT recalibration model (student) in details. The resolution peaks for each kinematic

VU9P FPGA	DSP	Flip Flops	Look Up Table	BRAMS
Available	9024	2.6 M	1.3 M	2160
Student	72 (0.79%)	5677 (0.21%)	11.3 K (0.87%)	0
Baseline	238 (2.61%)	11.6 K (0.43%)	33.2 K (3.38%)	0

Table 2: The table below shows the usage of various units of a VU9P FGGA when each model is run on it. The DSP reuse factor is set to 4 for all the experiments. Clearly, the student is much lighter compared to the pre-existing baseline.

quantity is plotted in figure 5. From the plot it can deduced the model performs well against μ GMT against all the metrics.

Next, resolution vs the reconstructed p_T is plotted in figure 6 which shows that the model performs well for low p_T ranges, but the resolution worsens towards higher p_T zones. This is since the number of high p_T samples is exponentially smaller than the number of low p_T samples. Plotting the resolution vs the Hardware p_T in figure 7 something interesting is observed. The model continues to perform well even for high hardware p_T values. This shows that the model is not at fault for low resolution in the high reconstructed p_T zone since only the hardware p_T is visible to the model during training, where it performs well. To understand the situation better, resolution vs predicted p_T is plotted. The figure 8 shows that the model mostly predicts small values of p_T and completely disregards high p_T , possibly due to the lack of high p_T samples in the dataset.

Plotting the $\left| \frac{\Delta(p_T^{L1}, p_T^{Reco})}{p_T^{Reco}} \right|$ vs p_T^{L1} in figure 9 it is observed that towards higher hardware p_T regions the relative error increases exponentially. This is the exact reason why figure 8 had not many predictions in the high p_T zones since making predictions in the high p_T zones is extremely difficult since the relative error changes exponentially; hence, the model resorts to predicting a statistically relevant (median) value to keep the error small. Similarly, on plotting $\left| \frac{\Delta(p_T^{L1}, p_T^{Reco})}{p_T^{Reco}} \right|$ vs p_T^{Reco} in figure 10 it is observed that the relative error between the two quantities is more or less constant. This is due to the fact that the reconstructed p_T is calculated after doing a full physics reconstruction in contrast to the Hardware p_T . Moreover, due to the low resolution of the data involved, it becomes increasingly difficult for the trigger system to calculate the hardware p_T with an increase in momentum, which is not the case for the reconstructed p_T .

p_T reconstruction resolution vs reconstructed η is plotted in figure 11. In this case, the student model consistently outperforms the μ GMT by a large margin. Next the results from Figure 11 and Figure 6 are combined into a 3D plot in figure 12 to understand the distribution of error better. The surface plots show the 3D representation of the error distribution vs. η and p_T . There are two surfaces on each plot. The neural network is colour-coded with VIRIDIS while the GRAY surface represents the error from μ GMT.

3.2 Fixing low resolution at high p_T

Although the model performs very well for low to moderate p_T values but fails to outperform the μ GMT in the high p_T range. There are several reasons for the models failure which has been discussed in previous section. In this section attempts are made to fix this problem. Two major techniques are proposed and experimented with as described in order to solve the discrepancy:-

- **Loss Scaling:** The loss is scaled to incentivise the model to work better for the high p_T region. The loss is scaled to the inverse of the number of samples in the dataset in bins of size 1 with similar p_T .

- Two Models: Since the model starts to perform worse for high reco p_T , intuitively one might think that using two models one for the low reconstructed p_T region and the other for the reconstructed high p_T region should be sufficient to solve the problem. Hence a two model approach is also chosen and experimented with.

Plotting the resolution vs the reco p_T for μ GMT, model with custom loss scaling and model with no loss scaling gives the figure 13 the scaling schedule is kept as shown in figure 14. The scaling does not affect the performance much for the muons in the low p_T zone although the scaling is orders of magnitude smaller still, the performance in the high p_T further worsens when compared to the non-scaled model.

Next, the two models approach is explored. Figure 15 shows the resolution vs reco p_T where a two-model setup is used during the inference. Although this setup solves the problem of low resolution in the high p_T region but it comes at a cost of degraded performance in the low p_T region. This is not because the model lacks learning capabilities. The low resolution in the high p_T region is only seen in the reco p_T and not in the hardware p_T ; since only the hardware p_T is visible to the model during evaluation, this method fails miserably.

Figure 5: Resolution vs ϕ , η and p_T for student and μ GMT

Figure 6: Resolution vs the Reconstructed p_T

Figure 7: Resolution vs the Hardware p_T . 1 hw unit = 0.5 GeV

Figure 8: Resolution vs Predicted p_T

Figure 9: $\left| \frac{\Delta(p_T^{L1}, p_T^{Reco})}{p_T^{Reco}} \right|$ vs p_T^{L1} .

Figure 10: $\left| \frac{\Delta(p_T^{L1}, p_T^{Reco})}{p_T^{Reco}} \right|$ vs p_T^{Reco}

Figure 11: p_T reconstruction resolution vs reconstructed η for both μ GMT and student model

Figure 12: p_T^{Reco} [GeV] vs η^{Reco} vs Resolution for μ GMT and student

Figure 13: Resolution vs reco p_T for μ GMT for model with custom loss scaling and model with no loss scaling

Figure 14: Loss scaling factor for different values of reco p_T for model in Figure 13

Figure 15: Resolution vs reco p_T for two model setup

4 μ GMT di-muon classification

Next, the interest lies in predicting whether a di-muon pair can be identified from a chosen pair of muons using the L1 parameters μ , ϕ , p_T , muon charge and reconstruction quality for both the muons. Offline reconstruction data is used as ground truth for training the networks. Knowledge distillation along with QAT is used to achieve a high level of classification performance by only using a fraction of the resources on the FPGA boards.

Teacher Model — A four-hidden layers neural network with 256 neurons in each layer is chosen as the teacher model. ReLU non-linearity is used along with batch-normalization after every subsequent layer. The output layer consists of a single neuron with linear/no activation. QKeras is used to train model with QAT precision fixed at [18,6]. The model is trained for 100 epochs using BinaryCrossEntropy (with logits) loss, and the learning rate is reduced after the model performance plateaus. Adam optimiser is used with an initial learning rate of 10^{-3} .

Student Model — A four-hidden layers neural network with 8 neurons in each layer is used as a student model. ReLU non-linearity is used along with batch-normalization after every subsequent layer. The output layer consists of a single neuron with linear/no activation. QKeras is used to train our model with QAT precision fixed at [18,6]. The model is trained for 500 epochs with BinaryCrossEntropy (with logits) as the task agnostic loss and KLDivergence as the distillation loss, the distillation parameter α is fixed to 0.1, the temperature is set to 0.1, and the learning rate is reduced after the model performance plateaus. Adam optimiser is used with an initial learning rate of 10^{-2} .

Student Model — A model identical to the student model is trained just using BCE Loss (without distillation) as a control. Every other parameter is kept identical to the student model trained in the previous point.

	Teacher	Student	Student-Non-Distilled
AUC-ROC	0.97	0.964	0.946
AUC-PR	0.887	0.86.8	0.85

Table 3: Table below shows the performance of the three models. Although the student is much smaller than the teacher, it performs almost as well as the teacher, being 1024 times lighter than it. It outperforms the non-distilled model, showing the advantage of distillation.

VU9P FPGA	DSP	Flip Flops	Look Up Table	BRAMS
Available	9024	2.6 M	1.3 M	2160
Student	78 (0.86%)	6110 (0.23%)	12.2 K (0.94%)	0

Table 4: The table below shows the usage of various units of a VU9P FGGA when each model is run on it. The DSP reuse factor is set to 4 for all the experiments.

The PR and ROC curves are plotted in figure 16 where it can be seen that for both the metrics the distilled model dominates over the non-distilled one by a considerable margin. Moreover the information loss during the transfer of knowledge from the teacher to the student seems minimal since the performance difference between the teacher and the distilled student is small. Also the confusion matrix is plotted for three threshold values of 0.7, 0.8 and 0.9 for all the three models which can be referred to in figure 17.

Figure 16: Precision-Recall and ROC curves for the three models.

Figure 17: Confusion matrix for the three models(top to bottom) for thresholds 0.7, 0.8 and 0.9 (left to right)

5 Dark photon reconstruction

The dark photon is a theoretical Gauge Boson. It is completely neutral under Standard Model (SM) interactions. Beyond Standard Model (BSM) particles have always been thought to be charged with respect to some of the gauge interactions of particles. For over last five decades searches with the above hypothesis have only failed. This shifts the research interest towards the dark sector. The motivation for exploring the dark sector is the hypothesis that no new particles are seen simply due to the fact that they might not be charged or that do not interact through the Standard Model gauge interaction.

The dark sector only directly interacts through the force of gravitation, making it incredibly difficult to detect. We expect them to interact through a portal which might take various forms depending on the type and the dimension of its operators. For now we focus on the Vector (spin 1) portal where the interaction is a result of kinetic mixing between one dark and one visible abelian gauge boson. In this work we try to explore the feasibility of neural networks to differentiate between backgrounds and dark photon signals produced at the LHC. Dark photons may be produced by Drell-Yan like processes. The backgrounds included SM mediated Drell-Yan, $J\phi \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$, $bs \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$ and a single neutrino gun.

Since this is a preliminary study and it has already been shown how using distillation-based approaches can provide both lightweight and accurate models, the training procedure and model architecture are kept simple. A three-hidden-layer neural network with 32 neurons in each layer is used for this purpose. The GeLu activation [6] and a dropout of 20% are employed. The model is trained for 100 epochs using BinaryCrossEntropy loss, and the learning rate is reduced after the model's performance plateaus. The Adam optimizer is used with an initial learning rate of 0.001.

Due to the rarity of dark photons, the dataset is imbalanced, with a significant number of negative samples compared to positive samples. To address this issue, four main techniques are explored:

- **Undersampling:** Given the dataset's imbalance, one can reduce the number of negative samples to match the positive samples by selecting a random subset of the negative samples for training instead of using the entire dataset. The number of samples in this random subset is kept equal to the number of positive samples in the entire dataset. Although simple to implement, this technique is often wasteful in terms of data usage, and sometimes the number of positive samples is too low for this method to be effective.
- **Oversampling:** In the case of oversampling, excess negative samples are not discarded; instead, the same positive samples are used multiple times. This makes the dataset virtually balanced since, after every epoch, an equal number of positive and negative samples are used to calculate the loss, equalizing the two sets in terms of cardinality.
- **Loss Scaling:** Loss scaling relies on the idea of giving more weight to positive samples and less to negative ones. Since the number of negative samples is much larger compared to the number of positive ones, weighing the losses makes the classification task easier by giving more importance to the positive samples.
- **Focal Loss:** The idea of using focal loss is somewhat inspired by the concept of loss weighing. Focal loss adds a modulating term to the cross-entropy loss itself, making the model focus on hard miss-classified classes. It is a dynamically scaled loss where the loss scaling factor decays to 0 as the confidence in the correct class increases.

Figure 18: ROC Curves for different techniques

Figure 19: Mass in GeV vs. AUC-ROC Values and Mass in GeV vs. TPP/FPR (right)

Weight (GeV)	Oversampling	Undersampling	Loss Weighing	Focal Loss
2	87	83	84.5	85.5
5	85.3	84.6	83.8	85
10	85.9	84.2	86.2	85.1
15	90	89.5	90.6	89.7
25	94.6	90.9	93.3	92.7
40	96.3	93	94.3	92.8

Table 5: Mass Vs. AUC-ROC

Weight (GeV)	Oversampling	Undersampling	Weighing	Focal Loss
2	22.51	1.47	20.16	2.9
5	7.45	1.98	7.094	6.47
10	4.56	13.55	8.735	17.91
15	2.98	70.82	11.51	2.79
25	37.16	52.07	71.5	93.27
40	163.13	55.12	94.6	47.2

Table 6: TPR/FPR at 0.001 Threshold

Figure 18 displays the ROC curves for various masses, employing different training techniques to address dataset imbalance. An interesting observation from the graphs is that, in all cases, the AUC-ROC scores increase as one moves into higher mass ranges for the dark photons. The AUC-ROC scores for different masses and techniques can be found in Table 5.

To gain a better understanding of the trend, ROC-AUC scores are plotted against the mass of the simulated dark photon. In Figure 19 (left), the mass in GeV of the dark photons is plotted against their respective AUC-ROC values. The plot suggests a positive correlation between the mass of the dark photon and the AUC-ROC score. Additionally, the ratio of True Positive Rate to False Positive Rate at specific thresholds, such as 0.001 or 0.1%, is plotted to provide insights into the model's performance. The corresponding metrics for all four techniques are detailed in Table 6. Figure 19 (right) can be obtained by plotting mass against this ratio.

6 Conclusion

In this work, various compression strategies have been explored to implement a lightweight neural network capable of delivering state-of-the-art performance, deployable on FPGA hardware systems in the CMS Level-1 trigger. A technique has been developed employing strategic combinations of quantization-aware training, knowledge distillation, and transfer learning to create a computationally efficient model with negligible loss in performance. The technique is tested on both classification and regression tasks, including μ GMT muon recalibration and μ GMT di-muon classification. The model outperformed the baseline significantly in the muon recalibration task, even after reducing the computational footprint fourfold. However, the model encountered challenges in the high reconstructed p_T region. Although an increase in the number of samples in the high reconstructed p_T might help to balance the dataset, it does not mitigate the exponential increase in error in the data itself. This study did not identify a concrete solution to address this issue, but the analysis indicates that the main reason behind this phenomenon is the exponentially increasing error in the hardware p_T compared to the reconstructed p_T . The proposed technique worked well for the di-muon pair classification task. Furthermore, as an extension to this study, the feasibility of using neural networks for dark photon detection is explored. The study demonstrates that neural networks can be employed in the triggering system to detect such exotic signatures in the near future.

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